

PROTECTING AND PROMOTING HUMAN RIGHTS IN WORLD SCENARIOS: A QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH

By

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Abstract: Human rights are the rights relating to life, freedom, equality, and dignity of the individual guaranteed by the Constitution or embodied in international treaties and enforceable by all national superior courts. The UN Human Rights Council is a United Nations body whose mission is to promote and protect human rights around the world. The council has forty-seven members elected for staggered three-year terms on a royal group basis. The headquarters of the Council are at the United Nations Office in Geneva is Switzerland. After the Second World War the United Nations framed the primary goals concerning the protection and promotion of human rights. It has established broad categories of universally accepted rights and established mechanisms as well as to assist governments in meeting their obligations to both promote and protect human rights. The purpose of this research is to provide information about human rights-related information, awareness, convey the mechanism, protect human rights, implement new procedures and fundamental mechanisms and fund treaty action plans, procedure and principles, human rights laws including children, disabled people, minorities, women, migrant workers etc. This research studies mainly deals with the rights of human rights and its related associated bodies works which one is dealing with the protection of rights and promoting the mechanisms with qualitative training programs and quality approaches for future generations to protect the violation against the human.

Key Words: Education - Rights- Human Rights- Fundamental Rights- Mechanism- awareness of human rights-treaty-Childrens rights- disabled people, minorities rights, women rights- migrant workers research – United Nation role for Human Rights - Primary goals – Councils- National Human Rights Councils- State Human Rights Councils- International Human Rights councils.

0. Introduction:

Human rights are for all human beings, whatever nation, religion, race, status one belongs to. Everyone is equally entitled to human rights without discrimination. The term human right is described as “the common heritage” or “common language” of humanity. These are internationally protected rights and are no longer exclusive “domestic jurisdiction” of the states.

1. Human Rights:

The Oxford Power Dictionary (1993) has defined human rights as the basic freedom that all people should have. These rights arise from basic human needs and demands. Laski defined “Human rights are necessary conditions of social life without which no one could become his best, to be himself holds good to date.” Human rights are sometimes referred to as fundamental rights or basic rights or natural rights. Kashyap has defined human rights as those rights to which every man and woman residing in any part of the world is entitled by being human. Human rights are therefore essential for a dignified living and personal development.

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Durga Das Basu defines human rights as “the minimum rights that every individual must have against the State, or other public authority, by virtue of his being a ‘member of the human family’ irrespective of any consideration.” Thus, it can be said that human rights are based on the dignity and moral value of a man. Human rights describe the norms and standards of human behavior. They are universal and egalitarian. Swami Vivekananda said, “If faith in ourselves had been more extensively taught and practiced, I am sure a very large portion of the evils and miseries that we have would have disappeared.” This statement clearly carries the message that a man must be truthful and benevolent towards himself, and towards the other human being, which will generate respect for mankind thus leading to a peaceful coexistence in society. Human rights help in creating a body of values and norms for human dignity, equality, non-discrimination. The right of an individual is very essential for leading a happy and prosperous life. If the political and educational system of a country is good, it could help in protecting and promoting human rights. When these rights are denied on any ground then it has given rise to political and social unrest, putting countries in very dangerous situations.

2. Human Rights and Indian Constitution:

Rights are claims that are essential for the existence and development of individuals. In that sense there will be a long list of rights. While all these are recognised by society, some of the most important rights are recognized by the State and enshrined in the Constitution. Such rights are called fundamental rights. These rights are fundamental for two reasons. First, these are mentioned in the Constitution which guarantees them and second, they are justifiable, i.e. enforceable through courts. Being justifiable means that in case of their violation, the individual can approach courts for their protection. If a government enacts a law that restricts any of these rights, it will be declared invalid by courts. Such rights are provided in Part III of the Indian Constitution. The Constitution guarantees six fundamental rights to Indian citizens as follows: (I) right to equality, (II) right of freedom, (III) right against exploitation, (IV) right for freedom of religion, (V) cultural and educational rights, and (VI) the right to constitutional remedies. There were seven fundamental rights in the Constitution. In addition to the aforementioned six rights, there was also the Right to Property. Since this Right created a lot of problems in the way of achieving the goal of socialism and equitable distribution of wealth, it was removed from the list of Fundamental Rights in 1978 by the 44th constitutional amendment. However, its deletion does not mean that we do not have the right to acquire, hold and dispose of property. Citizens are still free to enjoy this right. But now it is just a legal right and not a Fundamental Right.

(I) Right to Equality: Article 14: Equality before law: The State shall not deny any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India. Article 15: Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth. Article 16: Equality of opportunity in matters of public employment. Article 17: Abolition of untouchability: “untouchability” is abolished and its practice in any form is prohibited. The enforcement of any disability arising from “Untouchability” shall be an offence punishable in accordance with the law. Article 18: Abolition of titles.

(II) Right to Freedom: Article 19: Protection of certain rights relating to freedom of speech, etc. Article 20: Protection with regard to conviction for offences. Article 21: Protection of life and personal freedom. Article 21a: Right to education. Article 22: Protection against arrest and detention in certain cases.

(III) Right against Exploitation: Article 23: (1) Trafficking in human beings and begging and other similar forms of forced labour are prohibited, and any violation of this provision shall be an offence punishable in accordance with the law. (2) Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from imposing compulsory service for public purposes, and in imposing such service the State shall not make any discrimination on the grounds solely of religion, race, caste, or class or any of them. Article 24: No child under the age of fourteen shall be employed to work in any factory or mine or engaged in any other hazardous employment.

(IV) Right to freedom of religion: Article of 25. Freedom of conscience and free profession, practice, and propagation of religion Article 26. Freedom to conduct religious affairs Article 27. Freedom to pay taxes for the promotion of any religion Article 28. Freedom to attend religious instruction or religious worship in certain educational institutions.

(V) Cultural and educational rights: Article of 29. Protection of the interests of minorities Article 30. Right of minorities to establish and administer educational institutions Article 31. It is revoked.] Salvation of Certain Laws Article 31A. Saving of laws providing for acquisition of estate, etc. Article 31b of the Constitution. Validation of certain Acts and Regulations Article 31C. Saving of laws enforcing certain directive principles Article 31D. It is revoked.

(VI) Right to constitutional remedies: Article of 32. Remedies for enforcement of rights conferred by this Part Article 32A. It is revoked.] The Article 33. The power of Parliament to modify the rights conferred by this Part in their application to the Forces, etc. Article of 34. Restriction on rights conferred by this Part while martial law is in force in any area. Article of 35. legislation to give effect to the provisions of this Part.

3. Review of Literature:

Diya Ul Akaml (2023)¹⁴: The research answers to the open statement about Human rights are fundamental to who we are as God's creatures, and they must be respected, supported, and protected by the state, the law, the government, and our fellow citizens to preserve our dignity. (Law Number 39 of 1999 Concerning Human Rights). A. Mansur Effendi stated that human rights can also be referred to as natural rights, human rights, and fundamental rights. Human rights are the most fundamental rights that each person is entitled to due to their nature as God's creations. However, human rights are constrained by respecting those of others. (Article 28J the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia). Each person has a responsibility for fulfilling this, so it must constantly be considered when carrying out it. The state has a responsibility to uphold the law and defend human rights. Therefore, different issues that need to be dealt with with the existing legal norms must be accommodated by legal instruments. The law is the most crucial component in ensuring a balance between the affirmation of each person's rights and the performance of obligations. The law can prevent arbitrary acts carried out by one person against another or by the state against its citizens. The

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rule of law will underpin both state action and societal interactions. The normalization process, which is expected to produce formal validity and practical effectiveness, underlies the relationship between the establishment of laws and human rights. The goal is to create laws that are just, give legal certainty, and benefit society. Even though only legal certainty is assured to be achieved, there is still hope that justice will be upheld and socially beneficial will be provided. Articles 28A to 28J of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia define and protect human rights. The inclusion of human rights sections in this constitution is part of the 1998 reform demands. There were numerous instances of the state violating citizens' human rights, which sparked demands for change. The law appears to be a document created purely to support the continuity of governmental authority. The protection of every person's human right is now a key priority in the life of the country because of the inclusion of human rights in the Constitution. This is inextricably linked to the Constitution's standing as the supreme law, serving as a basis for all other laws that below it. (Law Number 12 of 2011 Concerning Establishment of Laws and Regulations).

Ahamed M A Hamad et al (2022)¹³: The national and international interest in issues of human rights and fundamental freedoms continued beyond the justification for emphasizing these rights and those freedom and approving them in the core of constitutions and national legislation and in many international charters. Instead, many priorities and measures were taken at the global, regional, national, governmental, and non-governmental levels to ensure these rights. However, an important act should be emphasized that human rights and fundamental freedoms are a national issue in the first place, given that national sources, in addition to religious teachings and the contributions of philosophers and social thinkers. According to some researchers' opinions, the contributions of philosophers and social thinkers are the original sources of these rights and freedoms. In addition, states generally work to stipulate in their national constitutions and basic law provisions emphasizing the protection of human rights and freedoms. It is noticeable that almost every country in the world is eager to include in its constitution or basic law explicit provisions that guarantee the protection of human rights and provide the necessary guarantees for their implementation. The authors recommend every country in the global stipulate in its constitution or basic law explicit provisions that guarantee the protection of human rights and provide the necessary guarantees for their application. For this, each state must incorporate human rights principles into its internal legislation, rehabilitate judges and persons working in the judicial organs and train them to deal with the human being as a human value and as an human being before dealing with him as a suspect or convicted person.

Ayesha Jawad et al (2022)¹⁰: The environment and human health have an inseparable relationship with each other; one cannot be considered in isolation from the other. It is important to understand their interdependence, as environmental pollution is a major global threat to the subsistence of humans and other living creatures. Environmental pollution is directly proportionate to industrialization as developing countries are heavily focusing on industrialisation; therefore, they are a major contributor to environmental contamination. Environmental pollution is generally categorized as air, water, and soil contamination since all three components of the ecosystem are essential for the survival of human beings. A healthy environment is essential for the preservation and protection of human life following are the

main types of environmental pollution and their impacts. Human rights and environmental rights are globally and judicially accepted by all nations in the meantime it will be protectable and must give more importance to it.

Verena Khal (2022)¹²: First, climate change is a meteorological phenomenon that does not necessarily violate human rights. Still, it is an anthropogenic phenomenon and States do contribute through emissions – either their own or emissions emanating from their territory or under their control – to global warming and its negative impact on human beings. However, climate change is neither caused by a single polluter nor limited to current contributions to global warming, as historical emissions continue to fuel climate changes even today. In addition, climate change is characterized by complex feedback effects and mechanisms of action. The causal complexity of the phenomenon leads to an essential time gap between the emission of greenhouse gases and the materialization of the harm that Pedersen describes as a “significant and forensically problematic delay”. As a result, it will be difficult to attribute a certain negative consequence of a climate change-related event to a specific State. Tully has therefore argued that “the human rights paradigm cannot address the disjunction between “victims” and their diffuse or distant “perpetrators” where “violations” are only predicted, rather than known and identifiable”. The question arises whether the current human rights system with its canon of pre-existing rights is prepared to address such complex questions of causality and attribution.

May & Dally (2019)¹¹: Pakistani courts have been among the first to recognize the importance of a safe and healthy environment for achieving the constitutionally guaranteed right to human dignity. Pakistani courts have made some of the most progressive decisions on constitutional obligations to protect the environment. While interpreting the scope of Article 9 of the 1973 Constitution, the Supreme Court held that this right encompasses not only the right to life protection but also to pleasure and quality of life.

Yordan Gunawan T and Azis M (2017)¹⁵: Currently, there is a blueprint for the establishment of the ASEAN Human Rights Court. On the way to establishing a regional human rights court for Southeast Asia, challenges abound, especially when rapid changes have revealed human rights violations in all nations in the region. It is not impossible, however, to establish an ASEAN human rights court if all ASEAN member states are willing to cooperate and ratify the convention regarding the establishment of the ASEAN Human Rights Court. By referring to the European Court of Human Rights, ASEAN can learn the successful way to establish and design its own human rights courts. Entering its new level of regionalism as a more united-visioned community by 2015, ASEAN had been put in the position to reform its longstanding principle of ASEAN Way, especially in view of human rights cases. As presented by the other regionalism practice, an idea of the regional court in ASEAN had a lot to offer. It is also considered as potential entry points in strengthening the community into a stronger regionalism, as it is aligned with the sole purpose of ASEAN. However, deeper research should be conducted in evaluating a proper blueprint.

4. Research Methodology:

To meet the objectives of this research, survey methodology was used to process the data. According to the relevance of the following elements: author profile, purpose, legal acceptance, Judicial review. Jurisdictional evidence implementation, awareness of human rights, children's rights, consciousness of fundamental principles, use to promote the new policy and laws, Government Gazette or Govt. publication information, and the related articles, case studies, books statistical package for social sciences has been adapted to analyze and evaluated to find the result. There are 96 research articles cited by the researchers related to human rights, children's rights, starting from 1995 to 2023. The researcher boasts that the majority of articles related to the Protection of Human Rights and its Implementation considered. 16% of articles only relating to the other categories i.e., environmental, natural, water, ocean, and others.

5. Need for the Study:

Every national government has enabled them to provide better service to the community. The study observed that few considerable types of points mentioned below.

- ❖ To know the different types of problems related to human rights.
- ❖ To know the majority reputed violation and demand by the public.
- ❖ To know the interest and awareness about human rights.
- ❖ To know the law and basic rules.
- ❖ To know about the criminal rules which is applicable to national regional and international levels courts and treaties or tribunals.
- ❖ To know the rapid recovery and precautions about Human Rights and its implementations.
- ❖ To know the key role and violation of fundamental rights in specific area with national evidence documents and orders.
- ❖ To know the amount of time, spend on implementing the new rules.
- ❖ To encourage cooperative efforts to save and share the Judicial authorities and their evidence at Asian, European, etc. level.
- ❖ To know the advantages of human rights structure and its mechanisms.
- ❖ Analyzed the purpose of using Human Rights and its importance.
- ❖ To promote efficient delivery of jurisdictional evidence with neighbouring countries and evaluate to promote and protect new policy and procedure through legal authorities.
- ❖ To know the future requirement of Human Rights Management Systems at global level.

6. Objective of the Study and Suggestion for the Future:

Objective of the Study: In this study, the following hypotheses have been framed: People are interested in using their fundamental rights, facilities. Research scholars are accessing jurisdictional documentary evidence for future development and its growth. The NGOs and professionals are eager to use full-text Government and Court orders. The Academic Institutions and Universities are playing a vital role in providing more awareness programs through researchers and funding or sponsorship agencies.

Suggestions: To contribute to the implementation of a world order based on freedom, lasting peace and social justice, ASEAN needs to establish a new human rights court. All ASEAN member states need to incorporate each other and make a convention on the establishment of an ASEAN human rights court. Then, all ten countries will ratify to make the status of ASEAN human rights court binding but the case that brought to ASEAN Human Rights Court only the case which cannot be handled by domestic court. The authors suggest the location of the ASEAN human rights court should be in Singapore considering that the lowest.

7. Data Analysis and Hypothesis Formation:

The researcher cited 96 documents out of 71 research papers, 5 Jurisdictional Proceedings, 2 case studies, 3 books, 15 International Conference proceedings which have been published in various sites for the purpose of feature innovative services.

Out of 96 publications, 73.95% of the author or researchers gave assurance for Human Rights and its features to protections. The majority (15.62%) of the Conference procedures are done and used for the Implementation of Human Rights Protection. The Jurisdictional documents and International Conference procedures are the backbone for protecting Human Rights and to implement to discover new innovative laws for the future.

From this study, the researcher analyzed the null hypothesis, Human Rights Law has more future to protect the public, children, women, employees, transgender people, etc. to fulfil the public demands in the future.

Rights and protection of Human Rights in India*:

Nature and Number of complaints 2019-2020

State wise no. of cases registered in NHRC

Nature of complaints of violation	Number of complaints received
Children	1019
Women	6796
Scheduled Caste/Scheduled Tribes	2405
Differently abled	297
Project affected persons	83
Communal violence	119
Health	1284
Business and Human Rights	57
Violations in Educational Institutions	466
Pollution Issues	458
Rights of Labour	1894
Violation of High Seas	11
Panchayati Raj Institutions	189
Denial of retiral benefits	1083
Inaction by concerned government	8268
Irregularities in implementation of government schemes	172
Death due to electrocution	377
Denial of benefit of government housing scheme	190
Rehabilitation of Homeless	67
Mob lynching	45

Sources from NHRC

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No. of Cases registered 2017-2018 to 2019-2020

Cases 'Dismissed in Limine' by NHRC during 2019-2020 (Total Cases: 17861)

Cases 'Disposed off with Direction' (DWD) by NHRC during 2019-2020 (Total Cases: 39923)

Cases Transferred to SHRCs by NHRC during 2019-2020 (Total Cases: 6801)

Sources from NHRD

Cases Disposed off by NHRC during 2019-2020

Number of Cases Custodial Death/Rapes Registered and Disposed during 2019-2020

Registered: 1700
Disposed off: 2174 (Including Disposal of Cases of previous years)

The Commission released Rights Awareness Booklets on Domestic Violence and Sexual Violence on the occasion of the NHRC-SHRCs meeting

8. Universal Declaration of Human Rights:

In February 1947, a group consisting of Eleanor Roosevelt, Pen-Chun Chang and Charles Malik began drafting the International Bill of Human Rights. With the assistance of the United Nations Secretariat, the task of formulating a preliminary draft was entrusted to John Humphrey, Director of the UN Secretariat's Division for Human Rights.

Principle of Universal Declaration of Human Rights: The principle of universality of human rights is the cornerstone of international human rights law. This means that we are all equally entitled to our human rights. This principle, as first emphasized in the UDHR, is repeated in many international human rights conventions, declarations, and resolutions. The following letter from the chairman of the Commission on Human Rights to the president of the Economic and Social Council dated 27 March 1947, (E/383), this drafting committee was enlarged. It was then composed of the members of the Commission on Human Rights for Australia, China, Chile, France Lebanon, the United States, the UK and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) is a milestone document in human rights history. Drawn by representatives with different legal and cultural backgrounds from all regions of the world, the Declaration was proclaimed by the UN General Assembly in Paris on 10 December 1948 resolution 217A as a common standard of achievements for all peoples and all nations. It sets out, for the first time, fundamental human rights to be universally protected and it has been translated into over 500 languages. The UDHR is widely recognized as having inspired and paved the way for the adoption of more than seventy human rights treaties, applied today on a permanent basis at global and regional level. (Contains references to it in their preambles).

Preamble: Whereas recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world, Whereas disregard and contempt for human rights have resulted in barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind, and the advent of a world in which human beings shall enjoy freedom of speech and belief and freedom from fear and want has been proclaimed as the highest aspiration of the common people, Whereas it is essential, if man is not to be compelled to have recourse, as a last resort, to rebellion against tyranny and oppression, that human rights should be protected by the rule of law, Whereas it is essential to promote the development of friendly relations between nations, Whereas the peoples of the United Nations have in the Charter reaffirmed their faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and women and have determined to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom, Whereas Member States have pledged themselves to achieve, in co-operation with the United Nations, the promotion of universal respect for and observance of human rights and fundamental freedoms, Whereas a common understanding of these rights and freedoms is of the greatest importance for the full realization of this pledge, Now, therefore,

The General Assembly: Proclaimate this Universal Declaration of Human Rights as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, in order that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this declaration constantly in mind, shall strive, by teaching and education, to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to ensure their universal and effective recognition and observance,

both among the Peoples of the Member States themselves and among the people of the territories under their jurisdiction.

Article 1: All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards each other in a spirit of brotherhood.

Article 2: Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set out in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth, or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made based on the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trusted, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.

Article 3: Everyone has the right to life, freedom, and security of person.

Article 4: No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms.

Article 5: No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

Article 6: Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.

Article 7: All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.

Article 8: Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law.

Article 9: No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention, or exile.

Article 10: Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.

Article 11: Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence. No one shall be held guilty of any penal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the penal offence was committed.

Article 12: No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home, or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks.

Article 13: Everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of each state. Everyone has the right to leave any country, including his own, and to return to his country.

Article 14: Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution. This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or from acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 15: Everyone has the right to a nationality. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality nor denied the right to change his nationality.

Article 16: Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family. They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage and at its dissolution. Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses. The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State.

Article 17: Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property.

Article 18: Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship and observance.

Article 19: Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.

Article 20: Everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association. No one may be compelled to belong to an association.

Article 21: Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives. Everyone has the right of equal access to public service in his country. The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this will shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedures.

Article 22: Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.

Article 23: Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment. Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work. Everyone who works has the right to just and favourable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection. Everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests.

Article 24: Everyone has the right to rest and leisure, including reasonable limitation of working hours and periodic holidays with pay.

Article 25: Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control. Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Article 26: Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all based on merit. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance, and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace. Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children.

Article 27: Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary, or artistic production of which he is the author.

Article 28: Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized.

Article 29: Everyone has duties to the community in which alone the free and full development of his personality is possible. In the exercise of his rights and freedoms, everyone shall be subject only to such limitations as are determined by law solely for the purpose of securing due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and of meeting the just requirements of morality, public order, and the general welfare in a democratic society. These rights and freedoms may in no case be exercised contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 30: Nothing in this Declaration may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms set forth herein.

9. Rights of Children:

In the industrialized countries of the early twentieth century, there were no standards of protection for children. It was common for them to work alongside adults in unsanitary and unsafe conditions. Growing recognition of the injustices of their situation, propelled by greater understanding of the developmental needs of children, led to a movement to better protect them. International standards on child rights have advanced dramatically over the past century, but gaps remain in meeting those ideals.

Timeline of Child Rights:

1924: The League of Nations adopts the Geneva Declaration on the Rights of the Child, drafted by Eglantine Jebb, founder of the Save the Children Fund. The Declaration articulates that all people owe children the right to means for their development, special help in times of need; priority for relief economic freedom and protection from exploitation and an education that install's social consciousness and duty.

1946: The United Nations General Assembly established the international children's emergency fund UNICEF with an emphasis on children around the world.

1948: The United Nations general assembly passes the universal declaration of human rights in which article 25 entitles mothers and children to special care and assistance and social protection.

1959: The United Nations General Assembly adopts the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, which recognises among other rights, children's right to education play a supportive environment and health care.

1966: In accordance with the international conventions on civil and political rights and on economic, social, and cultural rights, the member states of the United Nations promise to uphold equal rights including education and protection for all children.

1968: The International Conference on Human Rights is convened to evaluate the progress made by countries in the twenty years since the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. An agenda for future work is drafted and national commitments to uphold human rights are strengthened.

1973: The International Labour Organization adopts convention 138, which sets 18 as the minimum age for undertaking work that could be dangerous to a person's health, safety, or morals.

1974: Concerned about the vulnerability of women and children in emergency and conflict situations, the General Assembly calls on Member States to observe the Declaration on the protection of Women and Children in Emergency and Armed Conflict. The Declaration prohibits attacks on or imprisonment of civilian women and children and upholds the sanctity of the rights of women and kids during armed conflict.

1978: The Commission on Human Rights submits a draft of a convention on the rights of the child for consideration by a working group of Member States, agencies, and intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations.

1979: To mark the 20th anniversary of the 1959 Declaration of the Rights of the Child, the UN General Assembly declared 1970 as the International Year of the child, in which UNICEF plays a leading role.

1985: The UN standard minimum rules for the administration of juvenile justice detail the principles of a justice system that promotes the best interests of the child, including education and social services and proportionate treatment for child detainees.

1989: The Convention on the Rights of the Child is adopted by the UN General Assembly and widely acclaimed as a landmark achievement for human rights, recognizing the roles of children as social, economic, political, civil, and cultural actors. The Convention guarantees and sets minimum standards for the protection of the rights of children in all capacities. UNICEF, which helped draft the convention, is named in the document as a source of expertise.

1990: The World Summit for Children is held in New York. The guidelines for the prevention of juvenile delinquency outline strategies for preventing crime and protecting young people at high social risk.

1991: Experts from UNICEF, Save the Children, Defence for Children International and other organizations meet to discuss data collected from the reporting process of the Convention on the Rights of the Child. The meeting leads to the formal establishment of the International Child Rights Network (CRIN) in 1995.

1999: ILO adopts the worst forms of child labour convention, calling for the immediate prohibition and elimination of any form of work that is likely to harm the health, safety, or morals of children. UNICEF has been working with the ILO since 1996 to promote the ratification of international labour standards and policies concerning child labour.

2000: The UN General Assembly adopts two optional protocols to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child, obliging States parties to take action to prevent children from participating in hostilities during armed conflict and to end the sale, sexual exploitation, and abuse of children.

2002: At the UN Special Session on Children, child delegates address the General Assembly for the first time. The World Fit for Children agenda was adopted outlining specific goals for improving the prospects of children over the next decade.

2006: UNICEF co-publishes the manual for the measurement of juvenile justice indicators with the UN Office on Drugs and Crime. The manual enables governments to assess the condition of their juvenile justice systems and make reforms as needed.

2010: The UN Secretary-General issues the status of the Convention on the Rights of the Child.

2011: A new Optional Protocol to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child is adopted. Under this optional protocol on a communication procedure, the Committee on the Rights of the Child can file complaints of child rights violations and undertake investigations.

2015: Somalia and South Sudan have ratified the convention. The Convention is the most widely ratified of the Convention. The Convention is the most widely ratified international instrument with 196 states. Only the United States has not ratified it so far.

10. Children's Rights and Human Rights:

“All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.” “Everyone everywhere has the same rights because of our common humanity. We are all equally entitled to our human rights without discrimination. These rights are all interrelated, interdependent, and indivisible.

The international human rights framework: The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights

The United Nations set a common standard on human rights with the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948. Although the Declaration is not part of binding international law, its acceptance by all countries around the world gives great moral weight to the fundamental principle that all human beings, regardless of our nationality, place of residence, sex, national or ethnic origin, color, religion, language, or any other status, should be treated equally and with respect. The United Nations has since adopted many legally binding international human rights treaties and agreements, including the Convention on the Rights of the Child. These treaties are used as a framework for discussing and applying human rights. The principles and rights they outline become legal obligations on the States that choose to be bound by them. The framework also establishes legal and other mechanisms to hold governments accountable in the event they violate human rights.

The instruments of the international human rights framework are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the nine core human rights treaties:

- International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
- Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment
- • Convention on the Rights of the Child
- International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women
- • Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
- International Convention for the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families
- International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Forced Disappearance.

Learn more about these conventions: Every country in the world has ratified at least one of these, and many have ratified most of them. These treaties are important tools for holding governments accountable for the respect for, protection of and realization of the rights of individuals in their country. Understanding this framework is important for promoting, protecting, and realizing children's rights because the Convention on the Rights of the Child – and the rights and duties contained therein, are part of it.

Needs of Convention on the Rights of the Childrens: In 1989 something incredible happened. Against the background of a changing world order world leaders came together and made a historic commitment to the world's children. They made a promise to every child to protect and fulfill their rights, by adopting an international legal framework – the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. Contained in this treaty is a profound idea: that children are not just objects that belong to their parents and for whom decisions are made,

or adults in training. Rather, they are human beings and individuals with their own rights. The Convention states that childhood is separate from adulthood, and lasts until 18; it is a special, protected time, during which children must be allowed to grow, learn, play, develop and thrive with dignity. The Convention has become the most widely ratified human rights treaty in history and has helped transform children's lives.

Achievement of the Conventions: The Convention is the most widely ratified human rights treaty in history. It has inspired governments to change laws and policies and make investments so that more children finally get the health care and nutrition they need to survive and develop, and there are stronger safeguards in place to protect children from violence and exploitation. It has also enabled more children to have their voices heard and participate in their societies.

Childhood today: new threats, new opportunities: Despite this progress, the Convention is still not fully implemented or widely known and understood. Millions of children continue to suffer violations of their rights when they are denied adequate health care, nutrition, education, and protection from violence. Childhoods continue to be cut short when children are forced to leave school, do dangerous work, get married, fight in wars or are locked up in adult prisons. And global changes, such as the rise of digital technology, environmental change, prolonged conflict, and mass migration are completely changing childhood. Today's children face new threats to their rights, but they also have new opportunities to realize their rights.

Needs: The hope, vision, and commitment of world leaders in 1989 led to the Convention. It is up to today's generation to demand that world leaders from governments, and communities end child rights violations now, once and for all. They must commit to action to ensure every child, has every right.

11. Adolescent Development and Participation:

Investing in adolescents builds strong economies, inclusive communities, and vibrant societies. During adolescence (age 10-19), girls and boys begin to interact with the world in new ways – taking chances, learning skills, and experiencing unfamiliar emotions. They venture beyond their families to form powerful connections with peers. They look for ways to stand out and belong, to find their place in society and make a difference in their world. Today's generation of young people is bigger than ever before. But far too many are not getting what they need to realize their full range of rights. Poverty and deprivation, gender inequality and other forms of discrimination intersect with climate change, economic upheaval, conflict and displacement to threaten adolescent well-being. And through it all, adolescents are too often ignored by policymakers – or worse, seen as problems or threats.

Challenges of Key Facts and Opportunity: There are 1.2 billion adolescents worldwide – the largest cohort ever, and the most educated and urbanized. 90 percent of adolescents live in low- and middle-income countries, and 125 million live in areas affected by armed conflict. Sub-Saharan Africa's growing adolescent population, expected to reach 500 million by 2050, has the potential to fuel powerful change – if Governments invest in and engage it. Adolescents are the only age group among whom AIDS-related deaths are not declining.

Opportunity: The rapid physical and cognitive development that marks adolescence creates a critical window of opportunity. The adolescent brain develops at a rate unseen since

early childhood – making girls and boys hypersensitive to influences in their environments. Teenagers’ inclination to try new things can spark innovation and achievement, but it can also leave them vulnerable. These are the years when gender roles may be solidified – with girls bearing the brunt of gender inequality. The prospects of adolescents depend on the quality of their environments, relationships, and experiences. The care and support they receive, the services they can access, the social norms that guide their communities, and the extent to which they can influence decisions that affect them all make a difference.

Solutions: Investing in adolescents strengthens their ability to advance human rights and build a bright future for themselves, their families, and entire countries. UNICEF takes a life-course approach to adolescent development and participation, identifying critical risks and opportunities that have implications for the realization of children’s rights, from the first decade through the second. We address gaps in data to build evidence that drives action where it is most needed. Together with governments and other partners, UNICEF works to strengthen health care, education, and protection systems to ensure critical supplies and services reach the last mile, even in emergencies. We advocate for adolescent rights at the national level, while locally engaging families and communities – often through programs that change behaviors and social norms. Our emphasis on equity puts the most marginalized adolescents – including girls, those who belong to ethnic or racial minorities, and those with disabilities – at the center. UNICEF works with health providers to support gender-responsive services tailored to adolescent needs, including for HIV prevention and treatment. We support nutrition to fuel developing bodies and brains, work to ensure that girls have what they need to manage their menstrual health and hygiene and generate evidence on adolescent mental health. UNICEF works with governments and other partners to expand and protect access to quality, gender-equal education, and to improve student participation and learning. We work alongside adolescents to co-create solutions that support their transition into adult life and work, such as traditional and non-formal paths to education and skills development. To keep adolescents safe and supported, UNICEF works to prevent and respond to violence within families, among peers, in schools and online. We also address the growing risks adolescents face in humanitarian settings, promote adolescent-friendly justice systems, and address harmful practices such as child marriage and female genital mutilation. To expand opportunities for adolescents to participate meaningfully in their communities and the political processes that affect them, UNICEF empowers them to actively engage and express their views and opinions. We also work with partners, including youth organizations, to change the social norms that stand in the way, and develop platforms for adolescents to share their experiences and propose solutions.

1. EU-UNICEF Partnership promotes healthy lifestyle among Afghan refugee adolescents in Iran: ‘Adolescent Well-being Clubs in Iran are helping thousands of the most disadvantaged adolescents. “I was not able to say ‘no’ to others and usually I used to accept whatever others asked. (07 Apr 2019). Before joining the Adolescent Well-being Club, I had low self-confidence. But after participating in the classes here, I managed to improve my self-confidence,” says Golnar, a 17-year-old Afghan girl who, a year and a half ago, joined one of the Ministry of Health and Medical Education/UNICEF supported Adolescent Well-being Clubs operating in Karaj city, Alborz Province thanks to European Union (EU) funds.

Today, more than 2.5 million Afghan refugees reside in Iran, of whom some one million are “undocumented”. (without official residency papers). Many Afghan families and their children live in more disadvantaged areas of the country, requiring additional measures to

promote their well-being, especially those exposed to high-risk environments. As part of UNICEF's current country program of cooperation with the Government of Iran (2017-2021), and through funds provided by the EU, the Ministry of Health and Medical Education is being assisted by UNICIF to expand an innovative model called Adolescent Well-being Clubs for most at-risk adolescents, including Afghan refugees. The Clubs enhance young people's participation and increase their knowledge and skills on how to protect themselves against physical, social and psychological risks as well as how to promote a healthy lifestyle. Golnar is not only a member of one of these clubs but has also successfully persuaded several of her friends to join, among whom Aylar, a 16-year-old schoolmate, comments: "After my first visit to the club, I decided not to come, I couldn't connect with the others. But later Golnar encouraged me to join and now I am here, every day." She also remembers her past days of frustration and excessive anger. "I used to get angry very quickly but after attending the anger management workshops here, now I can manage my anger. We brought most of our friends here. We have found many friends," Aylar observes. Golnar is not the only Afghan teenager in the club because the staff have managed to reach dozens of refugees in the city through training courses at the club or at mobile stations hosted by partner NGOs, especially those dedicated to preventing Afghan child labour. Golnar and her friends have access to a variety of services including Life Skills training, HIV/AIDS and drug use prevention, HIV testing, and psychological counseling as well as music classes, sports, and recreational activities. But above all, they learn to live a safe and fulfilling life outside the clubs within their local communities. "[The club staff] do not ask us to limit our social activities, but they teach us how to be safe," says Saba, 16 years old. "If it wasn't for what I learned in the club, I would have used any kind of drugs found in parties," she reflects. Adolescent Well-being Clubs were launched in early 2016. There are currently seven operating in Tehran, Karaj, Ahvaz, Shiraz, Khorramabad, and Kermanshah. The clubs collaborate with other NGOs and take on outreach activities to provide access to at-risk adolescents in the most disadvantaged urban areas. Hamideh Abbasi, manager of the Karaj Well-being Club, says in addition to those Afghan teenagers supported by the club: "We are in the process of signing an agreement with an NGO with access to dozens of Afghans to offer our services to them. Undocumented families are not inclined to be registered in the clubs, so we try to visit them in their communities. We do our best to make them feel at home." With EU generous funding, Youth Well-being Clubs in Iran are helping thousands of the most disadvantaged adolescents, including hundreds of young Afghan and Iraqi refugees, to have access to skills and knowledge training, and services that help reduce social and psychological harm as well as promote a healthy lifestyle.

The Core Commitments for Children in Humanitarian Action: Since the Core Commitments for Children in Humanitarian Action (CCCs) were introduced in 1998 and revised in 2010, the global humanitarian context has changed significantly. Humanitarian crises are increasingly prolonged. Rising disregard for international humanitarian and human rights law and humanitarian principles characterizes conflicts, disproportionately affecting children and women. Population growth, urbanization, environmental degradation and climate change, large-scale migration, forced displacements, as well as public health emergencies increasingly compound the threats that children face. The CCCs have been revised to equip UNICEF and its partners to deliver principled, timely, quality and child-centric humanitarian response and advocacy in any crises with humanitarian consequences.

The CCCs form the core UNICEF policy and framework for humanitarian action and are mandatory for all UNICIF staff. Based on global humanitarian norms and standards, the CCCs set organizational, programmatic, and operational commitments and benchmarks against

which UNICEF holds itself accountable for the coverage, quality and equity of its Humanitarian action and advocacy. In addition, they guide every stakeholder, including governments and civil society organizations (CSOs), in designing their humanitarian action and in setting and meeting standards for respecting, protecting and fulfilling the rights of children. Humanitarian action for UNICEF encompasses interventions aimed at saving lives, alleviating suffering, upholding human dignity and protecting the rights of affected populations, wherever there are humanitarian needs, regardless of the type of crisis (sudden or prolonged emergencies, natural disasters, public health urgencies, complex emergencies, international or internal armed conflicts, etc.1), irrespective of the Gross National Income level of a country (low, medium or high), or the legal status of the affected population. Humanitarian action also includes interventions addressing underlying risks and causes of vulnerability to disasters, fragility, and conflict, such as system strengthening and resilience building, which contribute to reducing humanitarian needs, risks, and vulnerabilities of affected populations.

Are guided by international human rights law, particularly the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and its Optional Protocols, and international humanitarian law • Apply in all countries and territories, in all contexts, and to all children affected by humanitarian crisis, based on rights and needs, regardless of their country's state of political, civil, economic and social development or the availability of UNICEF resources • Provide a menu of minimum commitments, activities, benchmarks and standards that UNICEF commits to achieve in humanitarian crises, with its partners • Are grounded in the Sphere standards, including the Core Humanitarian Standard on Quality and Accountability (CHS), the Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE) Minimum Standards, Minimum Standards for Child Protection in Humanitarian

Action (CPMS) and reflect UNICEF's Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC) commitments (See 1.4.3 Global humanitarian standards). They are based on the Principles of Partnership: equality, transparency, result-oriented approach, responsibility, and complementarity to enable predictable and timely collective humanitarian action. Contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and include explicit strategies to link humanitarian and development action, strengthen local capacity and systems and build resilience at all stages of humanitarian action. Where appropriate and feasible, without prejudice to the humanitarian principles of neutrality, impartiality and independence, contribute to the UN system-wide agenda for ending peace.

2. Minimum Standards for Child Protection in Humanitarian Action (CPMS): The Child Protection Working Group defines child protection as “the prevention and response to abuse, neglect, exploitation and violence against children”. As there are threats to the safety and well-being of children in every emergency, child protection is an important consideration in all humanitarian action and can be a life-saving measure. Overall, the Minimum Standards for Child Protection in Humanitarian Action (CPMS) are intended to:

- ✓ Set common principles; Strengthen coordination.
- ✓ Improve the quality of programming and its impact; Improve accountability.
- ✓ Define child protection work; Provide good practices; and
- ✓ Enable better advocacy and communication on child protection.

3. Four guiding principles of the UN Convention the rights of the Child:

a). *CRC Principle 1 Survival and Development*: As well as the right of children to life, humanitarian workers must also consider the effects of the emergency and response on the physical, psychological, emotional, social, and spiritual development of children.

b). *CRC Principle 2 Non-Discrimination*: Emergencies often magnify existing differences and further marginalize those already at risk of discrimination. Humanitarian workers must identify and monitor existing and new patterns of discrimination and power and address them in their response.

c). *CRC Principle 3 Child Participation*: Humanitarian workers must ensure that girls and boys are given space and time to participate meaningfully in decisions that affect them during all stages of an emergency. Children should be supported to express their views in safety and these views should be taken seriously.

d). *CRC Principle 4 Best Interests of the Child*: In all actions concerning children, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration. This principle should guide all stages of the program cycle.

4. Four Protection Principles of the Sphere handbook on Humanitarian Response:

a). *CPMS Principle 1 Avoid exposing people to further harm because of your actions*: Those involved in humanitarian response must do all they reasonably can to avoid exposing people affected by disaster or armed conflict, particularly children, to further harm, danger, or violations of their rights.

b). *CPMS Principle 2 Ensure peoples' access to impartial assistance*: “Ensure that humanitarian assistance is available to all those in need, particularly those who are most vulnerable or who face exclusion on political or other grounds.” Assistance is provided without discrimination and is not withheld from children in need or from their families and caregivers, and access to humanitarian agencies is provided as necessary to meet the standards.

c). *CPMS Principle 3 Protect people from physical and psychological harm arising from violence and coercion*: Children are protected from “violence, from being forced or induced to act against their will,” and from fear of such abuse.

d). *CPMS Principle 4 Assist people to claim their rights, access available remedies and recover from the effects of abuse*: Children are assisted to claim their rights, through information, documentation, and assistance in seeking remedies. Children are supported appropriately in recovering from the physical, psychological, and social effects of violence and other abuses.

4. A. Two Principles Specifically focused on Child Protection Interventions:

a). *CPMS Principle 5 Strengthen child protection Systems*: In humanitarian settings, the child protection system or the people, processes, laws, institutions, and behaviors that normally protect children in a holistic and integrated manner may have become weakened or ineffective. However, the response phase may provide an opportunity to develop and strengthen national child protection systems, including community-based systems.

b). *CPMS Principle 6 Strengthen children's resilience in humanitarian action*: How successful children are in addressing and coping with their situation depends on the pattern of risk and protective factors in their social environments and their internal strengths and capacities.

The task of child protection programming in emergencies is to strengthen protective factors that reinforce children's resilience, and to deal with those that expose children to risk.

5. Standard to Ensure the Quality Child Protection Response:

a). *Standard 1 Coordination:* Relevant and responsible authorities, humanitarian agencies, civil society organizations and representatives of affected populations coordinate their child protection efforts to ensure a full, efficient, and timely response. Coordination allows everyone involved in child protection to agree on a shared set of objectives and division of labour. It can help create an inter-agency or multi-sectoral response that strengthens child protection systems in the long run.

b). *Standard 2 Human Resources:* Child protection services are delivered by staff with proven competence in their areas of work. Recruitment processes and human resource policies include measures to protect girls and boys from exploitation and abuse by humanitarian workers. This standard does not aim to replace standards developed by humanitarian agencies elsewhere, but rather provides a focus for human resources when mobilising child protection staff and implementing safeguarding requirements.

c). *Standard 3 Communication, Advocacy and Media:* Child protection issues are communicated and advocated for with respect for girls' and boys' dignity, best interests, and safety. Humanitarian organisations communicate and advocate on child protection issues, thereby bringing children's images and stories to the public. When used in a careful and strategic manner, communication concerning children can lead to advances in child protection. However, if used wrongly, communication and advocacy can negatively affect the way children are perceived and may cause further danger to children and their families.

d). *Standard 4 Programme Cycle Management:* All child protection programmes build on existing capacities, resources and structures and address the evolving child protection risks and needs identified by girls, boys and adults affected by the emergency. Child protection programmes must build on pre-existing information together with assessments (if needed). Children and their communities should be engaged in situation analysis, programme design and monitoring and evaluation. Analysis and considerations of existing child protection systems, and how these can be strengthened, should always be integrated into the programme.

e). *Standard 5 Information Management:* Up-to-date information necessary for effective child protection programming is collected, used, stored, and shared, with full respect for confidentiality, and in accordance with the "do no harm" principle and the best interests of the child. Information about a specific child for case management purposes may need to be stored and shared if necessary. Information about the overall situation of children and of the response should be consolidated, analysed, summarized, and used to inform programmatic decisions for the protection of children.

f). *Standard 6 Child Protection Monitoring:* Objective and timely information on child protection concerns is collected in an ethical manner and systematically triggers or informs prevention and response activities. Systematic monitoring of child protection concerns should be carried out from the first stages of an emergency. Monitoring refers to the on-going collection of information indicating levels and patterns of violence, exploitation, abuse, and neglect. Monitoring should always be combined with response.

6. Child Protection Needs: Standards to address Child Protection Needs are given below.

a). *Danger and Injuries: Girls and boys are protected from harm, injury and disability caused by physical dangers in their environment and the physical and psychosocial needs of injured children are responded to in a timely and efficient way.* After the age of one, unintentional injuries are a leading cause of death among children and adolescents. Children with existing disabilities can be at particular risk. This risk is heightened in an emergency. Displacement can also put children closer to previously unfamiliar risks, such as road traffic, rivers and floodwaters, unstable debris and explosive remnants of war. Injuries should be treated quickly and appropriately to avoid a greater chance of long-term or permanent injury.

b). *Physical Violence and other Harmful Practices: Girls and boys are protected from physical violence and other harmful practices, and survivors have access to age-specific and culturally appropriate responses.* Patterns of violence are heightened in humanitarian settings and children are more at risk of domestic violence, physical and sexual abuse and corporal punishment. Families and other sources of protection are often put under immense strain and the weakened protective environment around the child may result in family or community members abusing children. Families may also resort to harmful practices as a coping mechanism in the aftermath of an emergency.

c). *Sexual Violence: Girls and boys are protected from sexual violence and survivors of sexual violence have access to age-appropriate information as well as a safe, responsive, and holistic response.* In the chaos that can follow an emergency, children of all ages are at a heightened risk of sexual violence and are more easily exploited and coerced than adults. Sexual violence is present in all emergencies but is often hidden. Prevention and response to sexual violence against children should be addressed in all emergencies.

d). *Psychosocial Distress and Mental Disorders: Girls' and boys' coping mechanisms and resilience are strengthened, and severely affected children are receiving appropriate support.* Most children who have experienced stressful situations will initially show changes in social relations, behaviour, physical reactions, emotions, and spirituality. Mental health and psychosocial support bring together diverse, complementary approaches to providing appropriate care.

e). *Children Associated with Armed Forces or Armed Groups: Girls and boys are protected from recruitment and use in hostilities by armed forces or armed groups and are released and provided with effective reintegration services.* Children continue to be recruited and used by armed forces or armed groups across the world. Boys and girls are used in a few ways, including as combatants, spies, porters and informants, or for sexual purposes.

f). *Child Labour: Girls and boys are protected from the worst forms of child labour, those related to or made worse by the emergency.* In emergency contexts, with the possible loss of livelihoods, breadwinners and access to education, children become particularly vulnerable to child labour. While the child protection response in an emergency should be as thorough as possible, the response should prioritise the worst forms, starting with those related to or made worse by the emergency.

h). *Unaccompanied and Separated Children: Family separation is prevented and responded to, and unaccompanied and separated children are cared for and protected according to their specific needs and their best interests.* Children separated from their parents and families are at increased risk of

violence, abuse, exploitation, and neglect in an emergency. The prevention and response need to include actions to address the separation itself (prevention of separation, family tracing and reunification) as well as interim or alternative care.

i). Justice for Children: *All girls and boys who come into contact with the justice systems as victims, witnesses or alleged offenders are treated in line with international standards.* Emergency situations often increase the exposure of children to the justice system as alleged offenders, victims, or witnesses, or in a combination of these roles. For children in conflict with the law, detention should be a last resort, and where possible, diversion and alternative measures involving families and communities should be used.

7. Standard to Develop Adequate Child Protections Strategy:

a). Case Management: *Girls and boys with urgent child protection needs are identified and they receive age and culturally appropriate information as well as an effective, multi-sectoral and child-friendly response from relevant providers working in a coordinated and accountable manner.* Case management is the process of helping individual children and families through social services. Children should be appropriately involved throughout the process, and their best interests should be considered.

b). Community-Based Mechanisms: *Girls and boys are protected from abuse, violence, exploitation and neglect through community-based mechanisms and processes.* A community-based child protection mechanism is a network of individuals at community level who work toward child protection goals. Effective mechanisms include local structures and processes that promote or support the wellbeing of children.

c). Child-Friendly Spaces: *All children and young people can go to community-supported child-friendly spaces that provide structured activities that are carried out in a safe, child-friendly, inclusive and stimulating environment.* Child-friendly spaces are nurturing environments in which children can access free and structured play, recreation, and learning activities, to regain sense of normality and continuity. They require collaboration among sectors and should be designed and operated in a participatory manner.

d). Protecting Excluded Children: *All girls and boys in humanitarian settings have access to basic services and protection, and the causes and means of exclusion are identified and addressed.* Exclusion is commonly associated with stigmatized social status such as disability, belonging to an ethnic or religious minority, gender, or economic standing. Humanitarian crises can make exclusion worse but may also offer opportunities for change.

8. Standards to Mainstream Child Protection in Other Humanitarian Sectors:

a). Economic Recovery and Child Protection: *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of economic recovery programmes. Working-aged boys and girls and their caregivers will have access to adequate support to strengthen their livelihoods.* Economic recovery interventions should reach those households where child protection concerns are most pressing and should maximize children's chances to remain with their families, access education, and avoid hazardous labour or other forms of exploitation.

b). Education and Child Protection: *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of education programmes. Boys and girls of all ages can access safe, high-quality, child-friendly, flexible, relevant, and protective learning opportunities in a protective environment.*

Quality education contributes to the safety and wellbeing of children before, during and after emergencies. It requires close collaboration between education and child protection actors on a range of issues including child-friendly spaces and child protection prevention measures.

c). **Health and Child Protection:** *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of health programmes. Girls and boys have access to quality health services delivered in a protective way that considers their age and developmental needs. Health intervention is a central part of an overall approach to support services in response to major child protection risks in emergencies. Health activities must reduce child protection risks, and generally be carried out in a protective way.*

d). **Nutrition and Child Protection:** *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of nutrition programmes. Girls and boys of all ages and their caregivers, especially pregnant and breastfeeding women, and girls, have access to safe, adequate, and appropriate nutrition services and food. Children are particularly vulnerable to all forms of under-nutrition in times of instability and crisis. Risk-prevention measures should be included within nutrition activities.*

e). **Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (wash) and Child Protection:** *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of WASH programmes. All girls and boys have access to appropriate WASH services that minimize risks of physical and sexual violence. Child protection workers have an important role to play in making sure that child protection activities contribute to and maintain safe and appropriate WASH practices for and by children. Similarly, WASH workers should make sure that their interventions are carried out in a way that protects children and their caregivers.*

f). **Shelter and Child Protection:** *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of shelter programmes. All girls and boys and their caregivers have appropriate shelter provided that meets basic needs, including protection and disability access, and which facilitate longer-term solutions. Shelter is a complex sector with many implications for child protection. Vulnerability for children can increase during and after disasters, when children may be living with new, reduced or altered family units, or alone.*

g). **Camp Management and Child Protection:** *Child protection concerns are reflected in the assessment, design, monitoring, and evaluation of camp management programmes. The safety and wellbeing of girls and boys of all ages living in camps is safeguarded through camp management structures. The aim of managing camps is to create the space needed to deliver protection and help effectively. This affects child protection in several ways – for example, through the way the camp is physically planned, the way support is distributed, or the way decisions are made that affect children's lives. Camp managers need to make sure children are not exposed to risks in the camps and respond when these are identified.*

h). **Distribution and Child Protection:** *Children access humanitarian assistance through efficient and well-planned distribution systems that safeguard girls and boys from violence, exploitation, abuse, and neglect. Distribution of immediate, life-saving assistance is one of the most urgent actions to be taken in an emergency response, and one that can significantly improve the safety and wellbeing of children. The way in which food and other relief items are distributed has a significant effect on the threats experienced by women and children. Any kind of distribution needs to incorporate a child protection approach. It should be timely, comprehensive, and extremely well-planned.*

Minimum Standards for Child Protection in Humanitarian Action

12. Women's Rights:

The status of women in any society reflects the level of social justice in that society, and a woman is of that level of human rights in that country. In her society, the principle of equality between men and women is the most important pillar of human rights, and women's rights in general are among the critical issues that have become the focus of the attention of the international community, which called for the protection of Human Rights. These rights aim at the protection of women, the promotion of their status and equality with men in all rights without discrimination. This work is important because women acquire in the continuation of humanity, as they are the birthplace of life and the component for generations, and the need for them to enjoy their rights to improve the number of future generations. Therefore, it is necessary to know the protection provided by human rights law to women. The rights must be granted to them in addition to the mechanisms that help them to assume the position they deserve. On the one hand, due to the recent increased interest in women's rights, especially in some Arab countries, in which the political movement of women has increased activating the rights recognized in international human rights law, the problem of research appeared in determining the types of rights entrusted by international law. For this reason, our study will focus only on the rules of international human rights law and in explaining the analysis of the issue of women in international human right, not to mention the use of the descriptive and analytical approach due to the appropriateness of the form of our research. Therefore, in response to the problems of our research.

Women's rights in international human rights law: International human rights law is the law that governs relations between people of international law, whether states or organizations, and even individuals in peacetime, who possess rights and duties under this law.

Human rights are those rights that aim to guarantee and protect the meaning of humanity in various political, economic, and social fields. Accordingly, two requirements fall within this topic, the first: it deals with international law and gender equality, and the second is the role of human rights in preserving women's rights.

The first requirement: international law and gender equality: That principle of equality is one of the most important principles underlying any legal regulation of public freedoms and rights as it is the stronger principle contained in any constitution. It stems from other political and civil rights. The rights upon which a keen democratic society on justice and human rights and in the absence of women emerge in all societies and in different lives due to different conditions of inequality, whether due to law or reality. The degree of equality from the point of view of the law is that the law is applied to everyone without distinction based on a sect or distinction based on origin, sex, religion, language, or social position in acquiring and exercising rights, bearing obligations, and condemning them. Non-discrimination means inequality before the law and equality in its protection without any preference. The principle forms the basis of international human rights law. However, the distinction between persons and groups of persons cannot always be considered discrimination in the true sense. Equality in several aspects, including equality in the law, the judiciary, political rights, burdens and public costs, international charters and conventions have confirmed this by including in their clauses articles that guarantee the right to equality and non-discrimination in all areas and even though women are not explicitly mentioned in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The international conventions on civil and political rights or the international convention on economic and cultural rights, except that all conventions, include women in an implicit way in the context of equality. The concept of international legitimacy is used to refer to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the two optional protocols attached to it. These protocols are considered as the centre of the structure of international human rights instruments, which are International Human Rights Law or International Legitimacy for Human Rights in the broadest sense. This sense seeks to include, in addition to the previous components, the Universal Declaration and the Covenants, agreements, treaties, declarations and principles that favour the components of the international legitimacy of human rights and deepen their protection of rights.

The role of human rights in preserving women's rights: This role is considered the first contribution by the United Nations, it came in the charter of this organization ("The Charter of the United Nations (became effective) in 24 /October / 1945 review ", 1945). The charter affirmed any other rights that women can talk about, which is the right to equality, and the United Nations preamble defined equality in women's rights as a fundamental principle(2009, Nabil Mustafa Ibrahim Khalil).- In the text of Article (1 / Paragraph / 3), one of the purposes of the United Nations is to achieve international cooperation in promoting respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms for all people and to encourage this without discrimination based on gender (or language or religion).- Article (68) of the Charter also stipulates that the Economic and Social Council establishes committees for economic and social affairs to promote human rights, and it also establishes other committees that they may need to perform a function. Hence, the Commission on Human Rights is the only commission specifically named in the charter ("The issuance of the Declaration came with the consent of the semi - collective, as it received the support of 48 countries from the total 56 State of Iraq, including,

and who made up all the members of the United Nations at the time and without objection by any State,"). The importance of this committee stems from the fact that it is the institutional framework in which all international conventions related to human rights were drafted beginning with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948. In respect to women, the Commission on the Status of Women was established in 1946 as a subsidiary part of the United Nations Economic and Social Council. With a mandate to provide broad guidelines for improving the status of women in the economic, social and political fields, the Economic and Social Council was entrusted with the task of forming the Commission for Human Rights, drafted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on the 12th of December 1948.

It included a preamble and thirty articles that began in the first and second articles by emphasizing the three principles governing the totality of the rules and provisions related to human rights in the declaration, the principle of freedom, the principle of equality and the principle of non-discrimination. Also, there is no doubt that this declaration had achieved an important gain for women. Also, for the entire human group, it reaffirmed the principle of equality between the sexes in dignity and right. The second article stated that "every human being has the right to enjoy all the rights and freedoms mentioned in this declaration without discrimination of any kind, particularly discrimination because of race, colour, sex, language, religion, opinion, political and policy O, national or social origin, property or birth". It stresses that the right to enjoy these rights and fundamental freedoms based on equality in dignity and rights, which the United Nations Charter previously referred to, as an important aspect of political participation represented in the freedom to participate in peaceful assemblies and groups. Also, it focuses on the emphasis on election and nomination for elections assuming public office as a mechanism of participation and the necessity adopting gender equality in these rights, in the texts of the following articles:

Article (20): Everyone has the right for freedom to participate in peaceful societies and groups. No one is compelled to join an association.

Article (21): Everyone has the right to manage the public affairs of the country, either directly or through representatives who are freely chosen, and every person has the same right that others must hold public positions. Also, the will of the people is the source of government authority, and this will is expressed in fair elections that take place on the basis of the ballot. Confidential and equal for all, or according to any similar procedure that guarantees freedom of voting. However, despite its importance, the declaration remained limited, as it did not explicitly address the rights of women. Rather, it ignored some of them and confined themselves to declaring the principle of gender equality among a set of principles endorsed by the international community ("The Arab Network for Human Rights Information has developed international instruments that recognize the right of women,"). Moreover, the legal value of the declaration itself has been subject to controversy since the first moment in which it was issued, which centered on binding status of its provisions, and the possibility of initiating the international liability lawsuit against the states that violate the requirements of these provisions. The first believes that the declaration does not contain any legal value. It is nothing more than a recommendation issued by the United Nations General Assembly, while the other opinion considers that the declaration has legal value and constitutes an effective international reference. Regardless of the above controversy, it can be said that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights came in general to define the rights that should be enjoyed by people in general

in which women are equal. However, the spirit of the declaration was adopted in creating more detailed agreements for these rights and for vulnerable groups who need to highlight the need to enjoy them Equally. The first step in this path was the 1952 Convention on the Political Rights of Women. The Convention emphasized in its preamble that the main reason for preparing such an agreement is the desire of the United Nations to implement the principle of equality between men and women in the rights mentioned in the United Nations Charter. Then, it can be said that the United Nations attached great importance to the political rights of women, because this agreement preceded a historically speaking. The two international covenants (the International Covenant on Political and Civil Rights - and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights) are the basis for the text on political rights, of which participation is an essential part, in addition to that they preceded the Convention on the elimination of all Forms of discrimination against women. This convention demonstrates the importance of the role of participation in promoting women's rights, and this agreement stipulated exclusively several political rights (which together constitute the basic aspects of women's political participation) such as the right to vote in all elections, eligibility for elections in all bodies elected by universal suffrage, holding public offices and exercising all positions. The public and all equal terms with men in the texts are in articles (1, 2, 3) of this agreement. Thus, this agreement of the foundation was formed to assert the right of political participation of women on an equal footing with men and gave a legal and constitutional impetus to this assertion of rights. Thus, the text on these rights were included in an international agreement which obliges signatory states in recognition of the contents of the rights and consequences of this recognition of the rights of women that could invoke in exchanging for national legislation or practices. It has received the Convention and broad support from the countries of the world. This confirms the growing interest in the role of women in society, in 1963. The economic and social Council declared in the United Nations that most countries formally granted women the same political rights granted to men. However, this agreement does not include any mechanism to activate its work or monitor the extent of compliance with it.

Second: Mechanisms for protecting women's rights in international law. The interest in the rights of women in the world is evident through holding conferences, seminars and concluding international conventions at the regional and international levels to address all aspects and circumstances. All these contribute to the promotion of women's human rights and facilitate all means to protect them. Therefore, the researcher in this study deals with two requirements, the first: what are the international mechanisms that contribute to protecting women's rights, and second what are the types of international mechanisms? The first requirement: What are the international mechanisms that contribute to the protection of women's rights: It is meant by the international mechanisms in protecting the rights of women. It is the method and means adopted by the United Nations and the institutions emanating from it to ensure the implementation and monitoring of the performance and actual practice related to human rights and the preparation of reports for them. Therefore, they are universal legal guarantees that protect individuals and societies from the actions of governments that interfere with basic freedoms and human dignity, and to achieve human rights and ensure this. The various international bodies, especially the United Nations, have created a set of international agreements. They are considered indirect mechanisms that are signed by whom Desires from states such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention on the Cessation of Racial Discrimination. It also ensures the implementation of these agreements on the ground.

The United Nations established a group of committees with special mechanisms to implement and follow up the implementation of the texts and provisions of these agreements on the ground by the signatory countries and to ensure the amendment and development of local laws in line with them. All international agreements (previously mentioned) have contributed to the creation of mechanisms to monitor the extent to which states restrict their obligations in this field, including the submission of regular reports on the measures taken by states to implement the provisions of these conventions. Thus, individuals in some cases have the right to file a complaint against the state if their rights are violated, and many regional and international tools have been adopted on the protection of women's rights, such as international covenants, decisions, and recommendations. Many specialized bodies, programs and agencies within the United Nations work on developing women's human rights indirectly, as each of these parties assumes a specific role and responsibility under supervision and coordination of The United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights. An example of this is the United Nations Fund for Women and Children in UNICEF, which has a mandate to defend the rights of women and children. The International Organization for UN work (workers' rights), as well as the United Nations Educational, Cultural and Scientific UNESCO contribute to achieving security and peace by spreading the concept of cooperation among peoples through education, culture, science, and greater respect for justice and the rule of law and human rights and fundamental freedoms in the world. However, UNESCO works mainly to spread the rights to education and the right to freedom of opinion and expression, and to participate in cultural and political life. Many multinational organizations are active in the field of women's human rights and indirectly from these institutions: the European Council, the African Union, the United Nations, and the European Organization for Security and Cooperation. Likewise, many non-governmental organizations in this field act as an observer who monitors any neglect or non-implementation for human rights tools and as a catalyst for the advanced development of women and human rights laws. Also, the challenges and obstacles that stand in the way of implementing women's rights and human rights require serious analysis and the necessity to raise awareness among all parties to find radical solutions to the existing problems and those that are emerging as education in the field of women. In addition, human rights are one of the important means that works to increase the sensitivity of societies in general. Towards issues related to these rights.

The second requirement: the types of international mechanisms for protecting women's rights: The mechanisms for protecting women's rights varied. Of these types, they are international and regional mechanisms: International Mechanisms:

There are many types and international mechanisms to protect women's rights, including the institutional mechanisms established by the United Nations by internal decisions from its various bodies. Also, there are also agreement mechanisms that are designated bodies that monitor and control the implementation of international conventions. These mechanisms adopt the executive tool for implementing international conventions, a set of actions, including preparing and submitting periodic reports on practices and the extent of compliance with the agreement and the possibility of directing complaints between countries. They enable the individuals and groups to submit complaints, making recommendations to amend local laws in a manner consistent with achieving best practices in the field of Human rights and reporting to the United Nations and the supreme committees of international conventions. They are the first to take charge of protecting human rights is the United Nations, where respecting and protecting human rights is one of the main concerns of the organization. The Human Rights

Committee is the focus of attention, oversight, implementation mechanism and respect for human rights in the name of the United Nations, as the Council concluded, directly and indirectly, to establish a working group and rapporteurs on specific human rights issues to follow up and monitor their implementation. Also, according to the role of the United Nations General Secretariat as a centre for human rights, the United Nations General Secretariat considered a prominent role as one of the mechanisms for preparing human rights charters, following up on implementation and cancelling complaints about violations. It is based in Geneva under the supervision of the High Commissioner for Human Rights in the world. In addition, according to the work of international bodies in accordance with human rights charters, the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination found this committee as one of the mechanisms for monitoring the extent of compliance and implementation of the International Convention on the Elimination of Forms of Racial Discrimination. However, the Human Rights Committee was established by the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Committee on Economic and Social Rights, the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination against Women. These committees follow up on the conditions of women and the practices and violations issued against them. They submit recommendations and proposals to activate the role of women and raise their status. Then the Committee Against Torture is a committee specialized in stopping acts of violence and torture in its various forms for those who are practicing in their right either individually or in group. The last is the Committee on the Rights of the Child and aims to monitor the rights of the child on their rights in various aspects of life.

Second: Regional mechanisms for the protection of women's rights: These are agreements formulated and put in place by a role linked geographically, ethnically, or economically. Also, others are connected to agreements that guarantee a person his rights and serve these countries in their entirety as an individual person or as groups in this society. These mechanisms can be: The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights aims to protect human rights defenders. It is the primary means of protecting African human rights. The commission exercises oversight powers vis-à-vis the states party to the charter. In 1998, its member states adopted an additional protocol attached to the charter to establish an African court on human and peoples' rights. It entered into force in 2003 and, like others, enjoys judicial and consultative competence and receives communications from individuals and non-governmental organizations. The Inter-American Commission for Human Rights: It carries out follow-up work in the field of human rights to raise awareness of the community and deal with cases of violations. This committee was established after the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in accordance with a resolution of the Fifth Consultative Conference of American Foreign Ministers in 1959. It was entrusted with the promotion of human rights, as its quasi-judicial function is a monitoring mechanism for investigation. Its most important function is to examine notifications of states and individual petitions against states that commit violations, then the Inter-American Court of Human Rights was established in support of the Inter-American Convention on Human Rights in 1969, which is an independent judicial body with consultative and judicial competence.

The High Commission for Human Rights (Europe and Central Asia), the main task here is to work for the protection of human rights for all human beings. It also aims to help empower women to realize their rights and help those responsible to preserve these rights to implement them. The European Court of Human Rights, this court was established in 1959 and the purpose

of it is to create a collective guarantee for the provisions contained in the convention (Aziz, 1987). As for the Arab protection of human rights in general and women's rights, its decisions are still not serious in regulating human rights and far from what exists in the European and African committees that dealt with human rights. The Arab League Charter in 1945 did not include an organization of human rights. Then the Arabs activated and left the Arab Committee for human rights in 1986, which is an organization like the European organization. Then the draft human rights charter came to the Council of the Arab League in 1994, and the following mechanisms are most prevalent in the Arab arena, including the Arab Charter for Human Rights, the Arab Network for Human Rights, the Arab Network for Human Rights Information, the organization Islamic Cooperation, League of Arab States, Arab Labour Organization. This was an important aspect of the international and regional mechanisms and an active role of the international mechanisms in drafting international laws for protecting women's rights. As for regionalism, it seems that the index of the Western regional committees is larger and more operational compared to the Arab regional committees that contribute to preserving human rights, especially women. This is because the lack of Modernizing laws in the charter of the Arab League contributes to the existence of mechanisms that preserve human rights, including women's rights.

13. Rights for Physically Challenged:

"Don't be disabled in spirit as well as physically." – Stephen Hawking. In this universe, there are wonder of creations where there are normal and disable person living on earth. Nevertheless, all human is the same, nobody is perfect thus, disable person should not be left out nor isolated or being ignored and mistreated as second class due to their different on physical appearance. Generally, disable can be defined as a condition or function thought to be significantly or being labelled as impaired in contrast to the normal ordinary person born in the society. Hence, they are classified as lacking body functions or sensory such as sensory impairment, physical impairment, intellectual impairment, cognitive impairment, mental disability, and others. It brought to low self-esteem and ridicule as some people tend to stereotype, showing dislike, alienate by bullying, mocking, teasing or simply look down to this people. It is devastating fact and tearful to see some of these special people are being laughed by putting negative and insulting remarks such as bunch of hopeless individuals and being outcast in the society. Well folks, deep in their heart lies courage, strong spirit, and they shine beyond their limit incomparable to non-disabled. Being handicapped or having shortcomings in an individual's body is not an excuse or barrier to live with pride and joy, having successful career and pull off to the fullest like other normal human beings. For that matter, we must always respect and learn to be grateful for what we have, always believe in yourself, have sense of dignity, practice positive values, optimistic mind by showing capability and achieve your dreams. Nowadays, history tells and seeing is believing as we can see many disabled people do have extraordinary talents not only managed to carve success, victory results but also contribute to the society, knowledge, invention, technologies, and global economy. As the saying goes, still water runs deep so is "disability is not inability" people as it had been proven that these special are worthy able to contribute with their unique gifts and create marvels in the eyes of the world.

a. Learn to live with the impairment, know your capability and Strike for Success:

They are survivors, being independent, struggle for self-improvement, together with blood and tears battling the challenges to be excellent and at the same level with normal

person. Just to name several people born with impairment despite their imperfections they are inspiring prominent, outstanding and role model all over the world such as the genius scientist, physicist, exemplary researcher Stephen Hawking with his knowledge power and invention of science, Ralph Braun the founder of Braun corporation with his brilliant vision by producing wheelchair accessible vehicles giving the ultimate change freedom, mobility, and accessibility to the disabled person. Not forgetting the successful legendary blind song writer, musician Stevie Wonder with his contribution to the entertainment, Nick Vujicic a celebrity motivator, writer, activists, founder of Life without Limbs that operates organisation that supports disability people. Aaron Fotheringham a well-known astounding skater and specialised on Wheelchair skating and the Olympians Tani Grey Thompson for her massive championships in the arena of sports league. Some disable people thrive well in political, economy, advocates, and analysts. Something to muse, with these colourful achievements clearly explains that anyone be it normal or disable can do by bringing good influence, boosting our motivational thought, emotional feelings and energy to strive for endeavour. Indeed, the key to success is just by exploring; knowing your potential, love what you are doing and learning to do till succeed. It creates immense transformational from nobody to somebody. Nothing is beyond reachable.

b. Equal rights in providing education, social support, employment, and proper facilities: Something to ponder, Malaysians do you still remember the horrifying case of Bella the Syndrome Down teenager who being abused cruelly by the founder of Ramah Bonda. In fact, this shows that disable people should be treated equally and respected by the normal people. Now, these unacceptable conducts should be stopped as they are human beings that have feelings, human rights, and sense of belongings. Malaysian should have moral judgements and humanity by practicing virtues respect and aiding the disabled people. This is in line with supporting the Malaysian Sustainability Development Goals (SDG) SDGs 10, reducing inequalities in the society and SDG's 3 preserving the Good Health and Well-Being saliently. Remarkably, this special people prove that despite their health disability, there is no way out instead move forward by instilling self-empowerment through huge efforts sacrifices and goals to nourish triumphantly. This is because the bias and prejudice mind of some people by neglecting in giving equal opportunities on providing equal care, better support in education, best facilities, health care and job employment for them should be curbed. This is an effort in supporting SDGs that had been propagated which are SDG's 4 inculcating Quality Education. Moreover, normal people should open their mind by giving advisory, proper care, concerned, social integrative support by enhancing benefits for the disable, prolonging their social assistance and chances for being employed in job sectors. Believing their ability that they too can contribute in building the progress on political, social, or economic landscapes for the nation. Hence, it is also adhering to the concept of Malaysia MADANI, respect, trust, and compassion

c. Fostering civic awareness, tolerance, and acceptance of disability in society: International Day of Disabled Persons (IDDP) was commemorated in countries globally on 3rd December for every year. It first started on 1992, IDDP was proclaimed through United Nations General Assembly Resolution 47/3. Initially, IDDP aims to increase public awareness, tolerance, promotes better understanding, social rights, and acceptance of people with disability. In addition, this important event aimed to give huge appreciation and recognition by

celebrating their achievements and contributions towards the progress for humankind and development. Significantly, this amazing crucial moves and hope through the initiatives and involvement by non-disabled people in community will not only foster a healthy society but also shape quality social, culture, peaceful, serenity environment and public decorum for the impairment people. There should be an inclusion legal of rights or act protecting people with disability in Federal Constitution of Malaysia so that these special people are not discriminated, treated well, and respected in cultivating harmony, fairness, tolerance, and equitable inclusion as citizens.

d. Malaysian disable people making vast contributions from zero to hero: Behold Malaysian, we do remember the vast contributions of our Paralympic athletes for making Malaysian proud by giving valued performances in Tokyo Paralympic 2020 though in the amidst of pandemic. No doubt but this is true as they nailed it showing to the world that being disable is not a hurdle but a hardship to strive, live and tell by projecting confidence, positivity, will-power, motivated spirit to execute their priceless obligations in the sports arena. Abdul Latif Romly, Bonnie Bunyau Gustin, Jong Yee Khie, Chew Wei Lun, Cheah Liek Hou and others are the national gems and heroes that should be acknowledged with honour for their enormous patriotic deeds in Paralympic 2020 for the country. Profoundly personality, the extensive chains of 99 Speed Mart founder is a disabled wheelchair person, Lee Thiam Wah who made it against the barricades. Splendidly, his 99 Speed Mart nourished abundantly as it comprised of more than 1000 outlets all over Malaysia and three stores in Singapore. He who is known as the magnificent King of Mini Marts is a very dedicated entrepreneur successfully build his empire with his diligence, perseverance traits through his own hard-earned savings in making his dream come true. It is an inspiring to us Malaysian proving nothing is impossible in chasing your dreams and it goes with the saying hard work and determination counts. As a matter of fact, being disable is not an excuse and never be a barrier to reach the peak of success in life. Gazing to the stories, we recall the famous quote stated by the late President John F. Kennedy, “Ask not what your country can do for you but ask what you can do for your country.”

e. Wake up call for Malaysian; learn to accept, appreciate the disable in your circle: Finally, society should have social mores by showing concern, compassionate, holistic support and cultivate unconditional love and care as living with disability does not make you less of a person. Consequently, we should be conscientious by having empathy, tolerance, giving equal treatment, lending a helping hand instead of avoiding or excluding them out from the society. Malaysian people, do your part by accepting this special people for who they are by showing equal respect, have a sense of encouragement and support by inculcating humanity values to curb discrimination, misconceptions and eradicate social stigma on disabled person. Imperatively, the mind perception must be change for right-minded in fact “change begins with you,” with us, as individuals, families, society, and community. Remember learning to live with honour as true sensible Malaysian is built with good vibes, civilized, compassionate and humility.

14. Human Rights and Human Security:

The principled value base of the contemporary international human rights regime to which Southeast Asian states belong was first enunciated in the 1945 preamble to the charter of the United Nations reaffirming faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth

of the human person, and the equal rights of men and women. Article 2 of the charter states that a principle of the UN is "sovereign equality," which means that the UN has no authority to intervene in matters essentially within the domestic jurisdiction of a member. The tension between the international goal of protecting human rights and the domestic authority of a sovereign state has been the constant thread in the dialogue between defenders of rights and alleged violators. This tension is replicated at the Southeast Asia regional level in ASEAN's inability to reconcile its claimed commitment to the norms of democracy and human rights with its insistence that state sovereignty and non-interference were the bedrock of the region's international relations.

15. Researcher Result: The researcher has reached the following results.

Women enjoy, according to international conventions, many economic, social, cultural, civil, and political rights, such as the right to life and safety, the right to movement, the right to be recommended, the right to run for office, the right to have public office and the right to health care. The principle of equality between men and women in all rights is stipulated in international covenants such as the United Nations Charter, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and the International Covenants of 1966. The international community has established mechanisms of a global nature and others of a regional character to protect the rights of women, whether they are institutional or legislative. Also, the legislative mechanism is represented by international instruments of various kinds. The international organization, whether global or regional, plays an important role in protecting human rights in general and women's rights, such as the role played by the United Nations and its agencies. At the level of mechanisms of an international character, the Economic and Social Council plays a very important role in promoting and strengthening the protection of human rights, in addition to the specialized committees such as its human rights committee and the specialized sub-committees.

16. Regional Views of Human Rights:

Despite the UN's rights system's claim to universality, there is no unified view on human rights either globally or in Southeast Asia. To many Southeast Asian elites, the West's emphasis on civil and political rights in a democratic framework is the expression of a historical and cultural process in economically developed societies. According to ASEAN leaders, the preoccupation from West ignores economic, social, and cultural rights that are of paramount importance for the full realization of human dignity and individual achievement. The more extreme views see the West's human rights campaign as a kind of political or cultural neo-colonialism, particularly it is applied to trade and to aid based on rights judgements. The Western and Asian views were compromised, if not reconciled, at the 1993 United Nations Vienna World Conference on Human Rights. They consider the establishment of an appropriate mechanism on human rights. It was argued by ASEAN officials that a precondition for an ASEAN human rights body was the establishment of national human rights commission in each ASEAN state. National human rights agencies exist in only four ASEAN countries namely the Philippines (1987), Indonesia (1993), Malaysia (1999), and Thailand (1999). The establishment of an ASEAN human rights is the contentious issues in the charter's drafting. The CLMV body, a human rights compliance mechanism, has been included in the charter. No time frame was set for the foreign ministers and diplomatic to exercise common denominator

consensus on what the terms of reference of the proposed human body might be. With the authoritarian states holding consensus vetoes, it is unlikely that any ASEAN human rights instrument will be approved, or it will substantially alter the human rights practices of the undemocratic ASEAN states. It was the lack of credibility on the full protection of human rights in ASEAN that led Philippine President Arroyo to warn Myanmar to release Aung San Suu Kyi or the Philippines might not ratify the charter. One of Thailand's most respected political scientists bitterly commented that ASEAN's highly proclaimed charter has turned into a regional exhibit for Burma's intransigent internal repression and blatant disregard for basic civil liberties.^{11B} Extraordinary Crime in ASEAN Crimes against humanity are extraordinary crimes. The law of crimes against humanity has primarily developed through the evolution of customary international law. The terms of the concept of Human Rights Crime as an Extraordinary Crime in Indonesia still has many interpretations and there is no standardization of law, in a sense, what kind of crime that deserves to be included in the category of extraordinary crime. According to Muladi who tried to put forward some of the rationale for grouping an extraordinary crime. In the views of Muladi, the crime can be classified as kriminogen and viktimogen also potentially to harm the interests of various dimensions, from the security order, systematic or organized, threatening political stability, future development, and others. Zainal Abidin added some statement based on Muladi's opinion that in accordance with the principle of Intent Court, universality principle cannot treat several violations of human rights as an ordinary crime and as universal qualification of the crime against humanity. Based on the information above, extraordinary crime can be formulated that serious crimes against human rights because it has the specificity as described below: First, serious human rights crimes are against humanity as the background of motive power, carried out in a systematic and widespread. Second, serious human rights crimes result in the rending of the conscience of humanity, because of the enormity of the impact. Third, serious human rights violations betrayed the largest man on humanity. Fourth, human rights resulted in the emergence of serious crimes of terror, anxiety and fear in the community which can eliminate the public trust in the State. Fifth, serious human rights violations recognized internationally as the most serious crimes and even became an international jurisdiction if the settlement cannot be resolved at the national level.

Serious crimes against human rights can be concluded as the extraordinary crime. The crime has special characteristics and payloads, which is not the same and even more than the formulation of the evil that exists in the Criminal Code at the national level. Therefore, the handling of the cases was incredible and became a logical consequence to be categorized as extraordinary crime. The international community has recognized four types of serious human rights violations, the international jurisdiction, so that all countries that respect human rights can prosecute through the International Criminal Court (ICC). It is clearly stated in the Rome Statute of the establishment of International Criminal Court in 1998 that those four types of serious human rights violations namely genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes, and crime of aggression. At the national level, Indonesia only adopts two types of serious human rights crimes, both the crime of genocide and crimes against humanity, as stipulated in the Law No. 26 of 2000 concerning on Human Rights Court. These are examples of extraordinary crime cases that occurred in ASEAN countries:

a. Indonesia (Terrorism): On 12th of October 2002, two bomb attacks at tourist bars on the Bali Island which killed nearly 200 innocents, many of them are Australians. According to

Rosa, terrorism is not only an ordinary crime, but also has become a crime against humanity because it is so widespread and systematic, which has killed thousands of innocent people. Among those crimes were tragedy of the World Trade Centre, an explosion Bali bombing, a blast bomb in Madrid, London bombing, and many more. It is acknowledged that terrorism is a latent danger that will arise and continue to occur within the international society.

b. Thailand (Human Trafficking): Based on the 2000 United Nations Protocol to Prevent, Eradicate, and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially women and children, United Nations(UN) defines human trafficking as: The recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbour, or receipt of persons, by the threat or use of force, or other forms of coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, abuse of power or vulnerability, giving or receiving of payments or benefits to obtain the consent of persons having authority over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Human trafficking considered as serious violation of human rights.

It is because contribution to human trafficking is commonly believed to be related to poverty, globalization, and economic disparities among countries. An estimated one-third of victims worldwide were trafficked for economic purposes other than sexual exploitation (ILO, 2005a). In Thailand, the International Organization for Migration has estimated that currently there are about 1.9 million migrants in the Greater Mekong Sub-Region (GMS). In the past, a large influx of migrants into Thailand was due to war or internal conflict in other GMS economies. However, in recent years, migration from Thailand's neighbours was stimulated largely by economic conditions. A shortfall in low-skilled laborers in Thailand created a demand for migrant workers, from neighbouring relatively poorer economies with surplus labour. Although Thailand instituted a registration program for issuance of work permits to regularize the stay of migrant workers in the country, most of migrant workers in Thailand are illegal. Migrant workers enter Thailand through many channels, both legal and illegal, and in many cases, they become victims of human trafficking. Many of those who registered upon entry stayed beyond their permit period; others did not register at all. In 2008, an estimated 1.3 million migrants in Thailand were unregistered. Their illegal status, coupled with their general lack of understanding of the relevant Thai laws and their rights plus the fear of deportation, open them up to exploitation and harassment from their employer's stagnation. Sometimes, if such adverse events do not occur at their first destination, the migrants may be trafficked or led into forced labour at their second or third destination. Therefore, the distinction of whether they were cases of human smuggling or trafficking is often raised, but any conclusion needs to be treated with care.

c. Myanmar (The Muslim Rohingya in Myanmar): The Burmese military government claims that the Rohingyas are not indigenous people but have migrated from Bangladesh. However, even prior to 1962 Rohingyas were holders of government-issued identity cards and had also British-issued ration cards which affirmed they are citizens of Burma. Then on the pretext of checking these identity cards before the very eyes of the genuine holders of the cards, these old identity cards were forcibly taken and torn to bits just to refuse their identity. In February 1978, the Burmese military junta launched a large-scale program with military precision aptly named "operation Dragon King" (Naga-Min). The indigenous Rohingyas were persecuted on false allegations of violation of nationality laws ultimately leading to mass killing and expulsion of the Rohingyas from their land. Nearly ten thousand of Arakani Muslims (Rohingyas) were killed in cold blooded murder and over two hundred thousand were

pushed to Bangladesh on the plea that they are not indigenous children of the Burmese racial stocks, even though the Rohingyas already been there and existed for hundreds of years; the bones of their great grandparents are buried there. Before independence and particularly after independence there have been numbers of Muslim members of parliament (MP) and always two Muslim took a position in the ministry of cabinet till the 1962 military coup. During the army regime from 1962 to 1995, however, not a single Muslim was appointed to be a minister or even deputy minister. This is evidence of utmost discrimination against the Muslims in Burma. In purpose to Muslim administrations, State Law, and Order Restoration Council (SLORC) formed district councils, township councils and village ward councils. Even in the 100% Muslim villages in Arakan, army intelligence officers were placed to guard the Muslims. The Burmese military junta has a special bias against the Rohingya. Throughout 34 years of army rule not a single Muslim was ever appointed as judge in the Supreme Court or the Session Courts or even in the Lower Courts. Muslim schools were nationalized in 1963. Thus, there are not any high school at the time. Muslim headmasters and senior Muslim teachers were replaced with Buddhist teachers.

The Muslims concentrated on trade and cottage industries and became quite successful. The army junta, however, has continuously tried to dislocate them in various ways particularly through inhuman atrocities and forced mass expulsion from Arakan. Rohingya refugee movements pose a non-traditional threat to human and societal security. Traditional security concerns have so far always ruled the game. Global political power, geo-strategic and security concerns as well as economic interests complicated the security dilemma regarding Rohingya refugee issues, which made international community less interested in overcoming the current challenges. Political goals and political power contributed to ignore the potential danger of providing legitimacy to increase non-traditional threats emerging from the migration of Rohingya from Myanmar to Bangladesh and to other neighbouring countries. The research found strong support for the proposition in this case: the more severe the violation of human rights, insecurity, and repression, the larger the scale of the refugee flow. The more the refugee flow, the larger the non-traditional security threats. There is a positive correlation between the number of refugees and repression, the variety of which ranges from violations of human rights. Rwanda, Uganda, Kampuchea, etc. are also known for brutal mass executions. There is a clear link between migration and security as well. The perceived and actual threats were emerged from the plight of Rohingya refugee, from Myanmar to the border areas of Bangladesh and also to other neighbouring countries such as Malaysia, India and the Middle East. Refugee scholars are traditionally concerned with the human security of refugees, as they often flee to highly volatile areas and need protection. The security of refugees often threatened in host countries like Bangladesh. Because this country has been struggling with rampant poverty and encountered with various economic challenges. Moreover, there is a lack of adequate international assistance and interest from UNHCR and other international communities to solve the Rohingya problem between Bangladesh and Myanmar. From the perspective of the security scholars, the focus is on the security of the host society (citizen and state).

17. Establishment of the Human Rights Court:

a). *European Court of Human Rights (ECHR)*: Discussing about the establishment of ASEAN Human Rights court, it is important and instructive to refer to other regional human rights courts. Southeast Asia in successfully establishing and designing their own human rights

courts. Their developments may share important insight for many problems that Southeast Asia will probably encounter in the future. In fact, the international and regional courts have many lessons to learn from each other.¹⁴It's very important to distinguish the Human Rights Act 1998 (HRA1998) from the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, usually known as the European Convention on Human Rights. The Act is an ordinary Act of Parliament and is part of the law of the United Kingdom. The Convention is a legal instrument of the Council of Europe. (The Council is identified and explained later in the chapter). The Convention is not part of UK law. However, its content, the rights and freedoms contained in it, are given effect in the law of England and Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland by the Act. The Convention is interpreted and applied by the Court of Human Rights. Its judgements are not directly binding as legal judgments in the United Kingdom. However, both the Convention and the judgements of the Court are central to any understanding of what the Human Rights Act is about. They are also major source of principles followed by the UK courts when putting the Human Rights Act into effect. In 1998, the original two institutions created by the ECHR, the European Commission of Human Rights (the Commission) and the European Court of Human Rights (the Court), were replaced by one institution on which each of the parties to the ECHR is entitled to one judge. The jurisdiction of the Court extends to all matters concerning the interpretation on application of the ECHR. An individual, a legal person, an NGO, or a group of individuals can make an application to the Court alleging a violation of the ECHR. A member State may also allege a breach of the ECHR by another member State, but this is rare. An application will not be admissible unless all local remedies have first been exhausted. The application must then be made within six months. Applications can be made in any official language of a member State, but if the participant is careless. admissible, all subsequent documentation must be in an official language of the Court: English or French. The applications and pleadings are normally available to the public. The Court sits either as Committees of three judges, Chambers of seven judges or a Grand Chamber of seventeen judges. An application is first examined by Rapporteur (one of the judges) who decides whether it should go to a committee or straight to a Chamber. A Committee, by a unanimous vote, may declare inadmissible or strike out an individual application. Otherwise, by majority vote, a Chamber will decide on the admissibility of the case and, if it is declared admissible – but is not settled – on the merits of the application. If the case raises a serious question of interpretation of the ECHR or might result in a judgement inconsistent with a previous judgement of the Court, the Chamber may, before giving judgement, provided no party to the case object relinquish jurisdiction to the Grand Chamber. In exceptional cases, judgement of a Chamber may refer to a party to the case to the Grand Chamber, but it will be heard by the Grand Chamber only if that party accepts that the judgement of the Chamber raises of serious questions of interpretation or application of the ECHR, or serious issue of general importance.

b). ASEAN Human Rights Court: The issue of the establishment of ASEAN Human Rights Court has been discussed by the community of ASEAN itself. At present, there is a blueprint of the establishment of ASEAN Human Rights Court. At the 13th ASEAN Summit on November 18th to 20th, 2007, in Singapore, ASEAN leaders agreed to adopt the Charter of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (hereinafter ASEAN Charter), including an article

that mandates the creation of an ASEAN human rights body (AHRB). Since ASEAN has never had any human rights organ, the adoption of the ASEAN Charter could be viewed as a major step forward in the process of establishing a human rights mechanism for ASEAN. It is, however, too soon to have any sense of accomplishment. The process is not over yet. In fact, it has just started. The ASEAN Charter does contain elements that could affect the prospect of a strong AHRB. In the ASEAN Charter, the non-intervention principle retains its supremacy and is placed above the adherence to human rights norms. ASEAN values had established consultative style of discussion among member of ASEAN in resolving its regional disputes. The establishment of ASEAN Intergovernmental Commission on Human Rights (AICHR), transforming the ASEAN Human Rights Body,¹⁸ had been its realization. Under its Terms of Reference (TOR), ASEAN had affirmed such consultative style in their human rights settlement mechanism. It is ascertained that the nature of AICHR shall be an intergovernmental consultative body. Due to unresolved issues of human rights such as minority rights and human trafficking, AICHR role of advisory seems inadequate in addressing future challenges.

hat the region needs is a strong mechanism that consists of independent experts who can investigate and evaluate reports of human rights violations; consider individual complaints free from external interference; and make decisions that the concerned nations are obliged to follow. Regarding the procedure of the ASEAN human rights court, the blueprint has determined the rules of procedures, structure, and procedure before Thea SEAN human rights tribunal. As the proposed ASEAN, the Human Rights Court is expected to be a small human rights court, it should probably have a simple organizational structure. The first option is to establish a single-court formation, without dividing into smaller chambers or sections. The ASEAN Human Rights Court will then oversee making decisions on admissibility and making judgments on merits. It is very important that the procedure before the ASEAN Human Rights Court should be explicit, clear and transparent. Hearing should be open unless the ASEAN Human Rights Court decides otherwise. In principle, the judgments and annual reports of the ASEAN Human Rights Court should be made available to the public. On the way to establishing a regional human rights court for Southeast Asia, challenges abound, especially when rapid changes have revealed human rights violations in all nations in the region. While challenges should be acknowledged, they nevertheless should not be an excuse for doing nothing and do not eliminate the possibility of a human rights court for Southeast Asia. Compared to other regional states, Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand, and Malaysia appear to be in a better position to manage human rights issues and participate in the global framework of human rights protection. They have been more prepared to accept a more bold foreign policy and deeper regional cooperation. Officials from these countries have been more active in pushing for change in human rights matters in ASEAN because they all have independent national human rights institutions accredited with status “A” and a vibrant network of human rights NGOs that has been playing an important force behind any steps of human right evolution. Regarding the subject included, the ASEAN human rights court may compare from the nature of the admissibility of cases from the ECHR, the European Court shall recognize cases submitted by both individual and state parties. Much progress is needed to realize the idea of the ASEAN human rights court.

Although the implementation of such a proposal may proceed very slowly in the face of many challenges, evidence indicates that in a group of regional countries, positive change is possible and initial impetus may be created for further developments in favor of the

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establishment of a regional human rights court. It is time for the region to move forward and act towards that goal. Although human rights advocacy in the region needs to be patient and realistic, they should not hesitate in their actions. On the other hand, the obstacles to establishing an ASEAN human rights court are a high cost. At a minimum, some amount of money must be available to build or buy or lease an office for the ASEAN human rights court to arrange for the necessary facilities, provide accommodation for judges, and provide salaries to the judge, registrar, lawyers, administrative assistants, specialists, translators, interpreters, and accountants. This is not a small amount of money. Hence, it is not impossible to establish an ASEAN human rights court if all ASEAN member states have the will to cooperate. From the function of the AICHR, there are some functions that state that human rights protection mechanisms in ASEAN resist individual complaints, i.e. complaint of human rights violations as we know them at the national level. For example, an individual can complain to the National Commission of Human Rights or to the Embassy, even to the national Commission for Women. Nevertheless, it is proposed that the ASEAN Human Rights Court receive complaints from individuals but with the permission of the provisions that the state of the individual has ratified this Convention on ASEAN Court of Human Rights. Thus, if there is an extraordinary crime and resulted in one individual, the individual may bring the complaint to the AHRC, because it will accept individual complaints. The establishment of the ASEAN Human Rights Court is a step forward for ASEAN countries to realize one of its objectives which is to strengthen democracy, enhance good governance and the rule of law, to promote and protect human rights and fundamental freedoms by considering the rights and obligations of ASEAN member states. This formation will give a great improvement in the implementation and enforcement of human rights in ASEAN. Each individual state as a member of ASEAN has its own representative judge. So, there will be 10 judges in the ASEAN human rights court. But for the country that oversees the dispute cannot represent their judge to settle the disputes. If there are two disputed parties, the rest of the judge should have appointed one more judge as an ad hoc judge. It is important to make odd number of judges.

18. Training Programs Conducted by NHRC India: *Source form NHRC*

Training Division

INTERNSHIP PROGRAMMES

Conducted from December 2019 to January, 2022

S. No.	Month	Date	No. of Students / interns
1.	Winter Internship Programme	17.12.2019 to 15.01.2020	61
2.	Short Term Internship Programme	14.02.2020 to 28.02.2020	67
3.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - July, 2020	16.07.2020 to 30.07.2020	86
4.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - August, 2020	17.08.2020 to 31.08.2020	99
5.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - September, 2020	15.09.2020 to 29.09.2020	110
6.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - October, 2020	15.10.2020 to 29.10.2020	89
7.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - December, 2020	16.12.2020 to 30.12.2020	129
8.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - February, 2021	12.02.2021 to 26.02.2021	128
9.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - July, 2021	01.07.2021 to 15.07.2021	45
10.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - September, 2021	01.09.2021 to 15.09.2021	74
11.	Online Short Term Internship Programme - November, 2021	01.11.2021 to 15.11.2021	66
			954

19. Research Studies and Projects: (Source from NHRC)

Invitation for Expression of Interest for Research Projects: National Human Rights Commission, a statutory body constituted under the protection of Human Rights (PHR) Act 1993, intends to promote such research projects which are more focused along the lines of applied research or action-based research. The aim is to translate the research findings into an action plan to protect and promote human rights-civil and political as well as economic, social, and cultural rights. The commission invites expression of Interest (EOI) from the reputed research institutions, universities, recognized NGOs devoted to the espousal of the cause of human rights, The commission invites expression of interest (EOI) from the reputed research institutions, universities, recognized NGOs, devoted to the espousal of the cause of human rights, for undertaking research projects on the thrust areas or themes listed below:

I. Thrust areas/Themes of Research Projects:

1. Covid-19: Effects on human rights concerning employment and business.
2. Well-being/quality of life of persons living in old-age homes.
3. Nutritional care of children below 5 years of age: Challenges and way forward.
4. Issues of Refugees from human rights perspective.
5. Human rights ethos in Indian Culture.
6. Human trafficking: Issues relating to legal framework and its enforcement.
7. Protection of Human rights of the abandoned widows.
8. Victim compensation schemes under various statues: Challenges and way forward.
9. Ashram Schools (Boarding school for tribal girls and boys): Functioning and effectiveness.
10. New age bondage: A study of iniquitous bonds in education and employment.
11. Shelter homes for women and children: Functioning and challenges.
12. Promotion of Human rights in the local self-governance.
13. Disparities in equal access to education in “Aspirational Districts”.
14. Medical ethics and laws with specific reference to clinical trial of drugs.
15. Government residential schools for weaker section: Functioning and effectiveness.

II. Eligibility Criteria: The research grant would be made available to an institution having adequate infrastructure to execute the research projects(s). An institution which is associated in any manner with any aspect of protection and promotion of human rights, with good track record, qualified human resource and trained manpower, and which is not run for profit, shall be eligible to be considered for ensuring the research project, such as:

- i. Research and Training institutions set up and fully funded by the Central Government/State Government/Public Sector Undertaking:
- ii. Institutions/Organizations registered as professional society under the societies Registration Act, 1860 (Act XXI of 1860).
- iii. Institutions registered as “Trust” under The Indian Trust Act, 1882:
- iv. Registered institutions exclusively devoting itself to the espousal of the cause of human rights.
- v. University or a Deemed University.

- vi. College covered under section s(f) and 12 B of the UGC Act, 1956: Private college covered under section s(f) of the UGC Act, 1956 and affiliated to the university.

Note: In case of the institutions listed at S.No.(ii) above, their eligibility for receiving assistance will be decided by the competent authority of the commission after perusal/consideration of their registration certificate, audited annual report and balance sheet of the last 3 years, etc.

III). Procedure for submission of Project Proposal: The procedure for submission of the project proposal as per the prescribed format, selection/sanction of the project, release of grant and other conditions are given in the: GUIDELINES FOR SPONSORING RESEARCH PROJECTS”, a copy of which is annexed in the NHRC web page.

IV. Date and Mode of Submission: The eligible institutions/organizations may submit a soft copy of their research proposal in the prescribed format through email at ldr.nbrc@gov.in latest by 24/01/2022.

Conclusion:

The rights recognized for women, varied to include all recognized human rights on an equal basis between men and women, are the principle that, to it. Some countries have taken the path to concluding international treaties and establishing mechanisms aimed at advancing the rights of women based on the above. Currently, there is a blueprint for the establishment of the Asian Human Rights Court. On the way to establishing a regional human rights court for Southeast Asia, challenges abound, especially when rapid changes have revealed human rights violations in all nations in the region. It is not impossible, however, to establish an Asian Court of Human Rights if all Asian member states are willing to cooperate and ratify the convention regarding the establishment of an Asian court of human rights. By referring to the European Court of Human Rights, Asians can learn the successful way to establish and design their own human rights courts. Entering its new level of regionalism as a more united-visioned community by 2015, Asia had been put in the position to reform its longstanding principle of the Asian Way, especially in view of human rights cases. As presented by the other regionalism practice, an idea of the regional court in Asia had a lot to offer. It is also considered as potential entry points in strengthening the community into a stronger regionalism, as it is aligned by the sole purpose of Asian.

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